

FABRICATION OF DEPLOYABLE COMPOSITE STRUCTURE WITH MULTI-MATRIX DOSING PROCESS FOR ROBOTICS APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Origami-inspired deployable structures require materials that balance mechanical stiffness with foldability, yet most composites cannot localize these properties without compromising integrity. In this study, we propose a dual-matrix fiber-reinforced composite laminate featuring spatially tailored stiffness, fabricated through a novel dual-resin dosing and wet compression molding process. By selectively impregnating para-aramid and carbon fibers with compliant and stiff epoxy systems, we created monolithic laminates with both foldable and load-bearing regions. Thermal and rheological analyses guided the simultaneous curing of the two resins, ensuring phase compatibility and clean interface formation. Mechanical testing confirmed high contrast in flexural strength—707.7 MPa in stiff regions, 23.9 MPa in compliant zones—while Izod impact tests revealed over twofold improvement in toughness with the compliant epoxy. DMA and cyclic folding tests demonstrated excellent durability under extreme deformation, retaining over 90% of the initial modulus after 1,000 cycles. The fabricated laminates enabled the construction of Kresling origami tubes and other morphing geometries with minimal hysteresis and high mechanical repeatability. This dual-matrix system offers a scalable solution for integrating spatially programmable stiffness and flexibility in next-generation deployable systems across robotics, protective structures, and aerospace applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

Deployable and compliant materials have become increasingly vital in modern robotic systems, particularly for applications involving complex morphing, spatial constraints, and cyclic actuation [1]. As robotics evolves towards more adaptive, human-interactive, and miniaturized systems, the demand for materials that combine mechanical robustness with structural adaptability has grown substantially. These materials must withstand repetitive mechanical stresses and accommodate varying geometries without compromising structural integrity, making them indispensable in fields such as aerospace deployables, soft robotic manipulators, and foldable sensing devices [2, 3].

Conventional polymeric materials commonly used in soft robotic applications—such as silicone, thermoplastic elastomers, and polyurethane-based elastomers—provide adequate compliance but often lack the necessary tensile and flexural strength, load-bearing capacity, and durability under repeated mechanical loading. These limitations significantly restrict their use in load-bearing or mission-critical scenarios [4, 5]. Typically, such materials require additional mechanical components such as hinges and joints to facilitate motion, complicating system designs and potentially compromising structural performance.

Origami-inspired structures have emerged as promising platforms for achieving reconfigurable, lightweight, and compact systems by transforming two-dimensional sheets into three-dimensional deployable forms through strategic creases and folding patterns [6, 7]. These fold-based expandable designs enable compact storage, lightweight construction, and programmable deformation pathways. However, typical origami structures made from homogeneous monolithic materials, such as paper or polymer films, struggle to fulfill the simultaneous demands of mechanical strength and flexural compliance. Furthermore, their fatigue performance under cyclic deformation remains insufficient, primarily due to a lack of structural segmentation that allows localized property tuning.

Figure 1: (a), (b) Schematic images and (c) images of the dual-matrix dosing process based on wet compression molding.

To overcome these challenges, this study introduces an advanced integrated composite laminate approach that combines stiff and compliant epoxy matrices through a novel dual-matrix dosing method coupled with wet compression molding. This hybrid laminate architecture allows for precise spatial control of stiffness and compliance, creating structures that integrate stiff load-bearing regions with compliant flexible zones [8, 9]. By controlling resin deposition patterns onto fiber preforms, we introduce tailored stiffness variations that are beneficial for structures requiring localized flexibility and directional deformation capability.

Unlike traditional composite systems that rely predominantly on fiber orientation for property differentiation, our strategy incorporates mechanical anisotropy through dual-matrix resin differentiation. Additionally, this approach circumvents the complexities associated with post-process adhesives or mechanical joints commonly required in segmented composite systems. Crucially, the compliant matrix—an aliphatic epoxy synthesized from dimeric fatty acids—features significantly reduced viscosity and a controlled curing profile compared to conventional urethane-modified epoxies, which enables precise resin dosing, clear interfaces, and thorough fiber impregnation [10].

The development of this dual-matrix laminate requires careful control over epoxide ring-opening reaction kinetics, viscosity evolution, and interfacial bonding strength. Accordingly, thermodynamic and rheological analyses were performed to optimize resin formulations and process parameters. These analyses ensured complete curing and minimal intermixing between resin phases, yielding integrated composite laminates capable of enduring extensive cyclic deformation without structural degradation.

To demonstrate the practical viability of this laminate concept, we fabricated and characterized deployable Kresling origami tubes utilizing the proposed dual-matrix composite system. Kresling tubes were selected due to their multi-degree-of-freedom deformation capabilities, including axial compression-extension, bending, and twisting motions, which are essential for advanced robotic actuators and deployable structural components [11]. Mechanical testing and cyclic deployment evaluations confirmed that the fabricated composite laminates maintained structural integrity, demonstrated highly repeatable actuation performance, and exhibited excellent durability under repeated mechanical loading cycles, highlighting their strong potential for next-generation deployable robotic and aerospace applications [12, 13].

Figure 2: Kresling origami tube demonstrating reversible transformation between compact and expanded states. Stacked configurations enable multi-degree-of-freedom deformation, including axial, bending, and twisting motion, suitable for robotic articulation.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Stiff epoxy consisted of Bisphenol A diglycidyl ether (DGEBA)-based epoxy (KFR-120V) with an epoxide equivalent weight (E.E.W.) of 200 g/eq and amine hardener (KFH-163) with an amine hydrogen equivalent weight (A.H.E.W.) of 58.1g/eq. Compliant epoxy was synthesized from dimeric fatty acid-based aliphatic epoxy with an E.E.W. of 430 g/eq and G640 hardener with an A.H.E.W. of 110 g/eq (Kukdo Chemical, Korea). Fiber reinforcements included plain-weave carbon (208 g/m², Hyundai Fiber) and para-aramid fabrics (180 g/m², Taekwang).

2.2 Resin characterization

To optimize the molding conditions for the dual epoxy resin system consisting of DGEBA and

aliphatic epoxy matrices, rheological and thermodynamic analyses were conducted using a rotational rheometer and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), respectively. A rotational rheometer (MCR 702e, Anton Paar, Austria) equipped with a 25 mm parallel plate geometry was used to characterize the temperature-dependent viscosity of each resin system. A temperature sweep was conducted from 30 to 200 °C at a heating rate of 5 °C/min, 1 Hz frequency, and 0.1% strain. The curing behavior of each resin was investigated using a DSC (Q20, TA Instruments, USA) under a nitrogen atmosphere. Dynamic scans were performed from 30 to 220 °C at 5 °C/min to determine the total heat of epoxide ring-opening reaction and curing onset temperature. Isothermal scans were conducted to calculate the degree of cure, confirming that both resins achieved over 90% conversion within 30 min.

2.3 Composite fabrication

Composite laminates were fabricated using a dual-matrix dosing process combined with wet compression molding. Plain weave fiber reinforcements were precisely cut and arranged into designed laminate architectures, consisting of compliant and stiff regions. The compliant sections were composed of a single ply of plain-weave *p*-aramid fabric. The stiff sections were constructed by stacking two plies of plain-weave carbon fabric over one ply of *p*-aramid fabric in a [0/90] cross-ply configuration.

Each resin system was degassed under vacuum at 60 °C for 20 min to remove entrapped air. Resin dosing was performed by a programmable pneumatic dosing system (WINC V1, Nordson EFD, USA) equipped with a 55 mL syringe and a 0.063'' inner diameter tip. The dosing head traversed at a constant speed of 0.6 mm/s with a discharge pressure of 0.5 psi. The distance between the tip and the fiber surfaces was maintained at 0.5 mm, and the resin temperature was held at 60 °C during dosing to ensure stable viscosity and precise flow control.

Following deposition, the preforms were consolidated via wet compression molding at 160 °C under a pressure of 5 MPa for 30 min. This process ensured full curing of both resin systems, sharp interfacial boundaries between regions, and uniform fiber wet-out, resulting in a monolithic laminate with embedded spatially graded compliance suitable for deployable applications. The thicknesses of the obtained laminate's compliant section and stiff section were 0.25 mm and 0.70 mm, respectively.

2.4 Mechanical testing

To evaluate the mechanical performance of the dual-matrix composite system, separate specimens were fabricated using either the stiff or the compliant epoxy formulation. Compliant FRP specimens were prepared using four plies of plain-weave *p*-aramid fabrics while maintaining the same overall fiber volume fraction as the single ply of *p*-aramid fabric counterparts to ensure direct comparability.

Flexural properties were measured based on ASTM D790 using 60 mm × 25 mm rectangular specimens in a three-point bending configuration with a universal testing machine (RB301, Unitech, R&B, Korea). The span length was set to 32 mm, and the crosshead speed was 0.85 mm/min. The upper loading nose and lower support rollers had diameters of 9 mm and 3 mm, respectively.

Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA, MCR 702e, Anton Paar, Austria) was conducted to evaluate the viscoelastic properties of stiff and compliant sections. Rectangular specimens measuring 60 mm × 10 mm were analyzed using a dual-cantilever bending configuration. Measurements were performed at a frequency of 1 Hz, a strain amplitude of 0.1%, and temperatures ranging from 50 to 200 °C at a heating rate of 5 °C/min. Additionally, cyclic bending durability tests were conducted on a 1 mm-thick compliant composite laminate (4-ply *p*-aramid), applying 1,000 bending cycles at a frequency of 1 Hz and a cyclic amplitude of 1,000% in single-cantilever mode.

Izod impact tests were performed according to ASTM D256 using an Izod pendulum impact tester (CEAST 9050, Instron, equipped with a 22 J hammer). Four different composite laminates—carbon/DGEBA epoxy, carbon/compliant epoxy, *p*-aramid/DGEBA epoxy, and *p*-aramid/compliant epoxy—were tested to systematically investigate the effects of fiber type and matrix stiffness on impact

resistance.

The compressive deployment behavior of the fabricated Kresling origami tubes was evaluated under cyclic strain conditions. The tubes were repeatedly compressed and re-expanded between 30% and 80% axial strain for 10 cycles. Load–displacement behavior and shape recovery were monitored to assess mechanical integrity, actuation repeatability, and fatigue resistance during transformation.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Resin optimization for dual-matrix injection

To enable simultaneous impregnation and curing of the stiff and compliant epoxy systems, comprehensive thermal and rheological analyses were conducted to determine the optimal processing window.

Figure 3: Temperature-dependent viscosity of the compliant epoxy measured by rheometer dynamic scan.

Rheological analysis was conducted to determine a suitable processing window for the compliant epoxy system. As shown in Figure 3, the complex viscosity remained relatively constant around 2 Pa·s across a broad temperature range from 50 °C to 160 °C, indicating excellent flow stability suitable for liquid molding. A sharp increase in viscosity was observed beyond 160 °C, corresponding to the onset of epoxide ring-opening and gelation reactions, marking the transition to rapid crosslinking and network formation.

Based on this behavior, the molding temperature was set to 60 °C to maintain low viscosity and ensure uniform resin distribution during dispensing. The curing temperature was set to 160 °C to initiate and complete crosslinking within a practical processing time. This temperature regime provided sufficient flowability during impregnation while ensuring rapid gelation and full curing during compression molding.

Figure 4: Dynamic DSC curves of (a) DGEBA epoxy and (b) compliant epoxy

As shown in Figure 4, dynamic DSC measurements revealed that the DGEBA-based stiff epoxy exhibited a reaction enthalpy of 483.41 J/g, indicating rapid crosslinking and high reactivity. In contrast, the compliant epoxy exhibited a lower enthalpy of 172.04 J/g, suggesting slower and more gradual curing behavior suitable for spatially controlled processing. To further assess curing kinetics, isothermal DSC scans were performed, and the degree of cure was calculated. The resulting conversion profiles confirmed that both epoxy systems reached over 90% cure within 30 min at 160 °C, demonstrating compatibility for concurrent curing in a dual-matrix system.

Based on these analyses, the processing conditions for the dual-resin system were established as follows: dispensing at 60 °C for low-viscosity flow and mold wet-out, followed by compression molding and curing at 160 °C, enabling complete crosslinking without premature gelation. These conditions ensured sharp interface formation, uniform fiber impregnation, and full structural integration between stiff and compliant regions.

3.2 Resin-fiber and resin-resin interface

Figure 5: Resin intermixing behavior and interfacial compatibility in dual-matrix laminate structures. Cross-sectional optical microscopy images of (a) the stiff epoxy region and (b) the compliant epoxy region. (c) Schematic illustrating slight resin intermixing during impregnation.

Since both stiff and compliant matrices are epoxy-based thermoset processed via the liquid molding process, significant phase separation or poor interfacial adhesion was not observed. Due to resin impregnation dynamics, the lower side reveals some penetration of the DGEBA epoxy (~100 mPa·s, yellow) into the compliant epoxy region (~2 Pa·s, blue), resulting in indistinct boundaries and molecular-level mixing without notable phase separation. In Figure 5(a), Cross-sectional micrographs show carbon and *p*-aramid fiber layers within the stiff epoxy section, with a low void content. Similarly, Figure 5(b) indicates through impregnation of compliant epoxy within the *p*-aramid fiber region, it also exhibits low void content and confirms excellent resin-fiber compatibility.

3.3 Mechanical behavior of stiff and compliant sections

Figure 6: (a) Flexural strength of laminates with different fiber-resin combinations. (b) Corresponding flexural stress-strain curves.

To investigate the effect of the compliant epoxy matrix on flexural properties, four composite laminates were tested with different combinations of fiber type and matrix stiffness, as shown in Figure 6. The stiff section, composed of two plies of carbon fabric and one ply of *p*-aramid fabric impregnated with DGEBA epoxy, exhibited the highest flexural strength (707.7 MPa). This superior rigidity ensures that the stiff regions maintain their planar geometry during deployment, enabling well-defined crease lines in the origami structure. The DGEBA-*p*-aramid specimen also showed a relatively high flexural strength (166.3 MPa), although the lower fiber modulus compared to carbon led to more compliance. This confirms that structural rigidity in origami systems is primarily governed by the carbon fiber-DGEBA combination.

In contrast, the compliant section, composed of *p*-aramid fabric impregnated with the compliant epoxy, showed a significantly lower flexural strength (23.9 MPa), allowing for easy and localized bending. The laminate remained unbroken even when bent until the jigs made contact, indicating excellent ductility. Interestingly, the carbon-compliant epoxy laminate exhibited a flexural strength of 55.0 MPa, significantly lower than its DGEBA counterpart, confirming that matrix stiffness has a dominant influence on bending resistance. Moreover, the high strain-to-failure observed in both compliant laminates indicates their suitability for foldable zones within deployable structures.

Figure 7: Temperature ramp DMA results of the (a) stiff and (b) compliant section

Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) results for the stiff and compliant composite sections are presented in Figure 7. Figure 7(a) shows the temperature-dependent viscoelastic behavior of the stiff section during a temperature ramp test. The storage modulus remains high up to approximately 100 °C, indicating that the stiff section effectively maintains its structural rigidity under typical use conditions. However, the sharp drop in modulus beyond 108 °C, coinciding with the $\tan \delta$ peak (T_g), suggests that the material may lose its load-bearing capacity at elevated temperatures, becoming susceptible to folding or deformation. In contrast, Figure 7(b) demonstrates that the compliant section exhibits a relatively low but stable storage modulus across the entire temperature range. The nearly constant storage modulus and $\tan \delta$ indicate thermally stable softness, making the compliant section highly suitable for applications requiring repeated bending. While the soft epoxy ensures excellent flexibility at room temperature, its T_g was separately confirmed to be below -20 °C, implying that the material becomes stiff under sub-zero conditions and may not be suitable for cryogenic or arctic applications. At room temperature, the storage modulus of the stiff section is nearly two orders of magnitude higher than that of the compliant section, establishing a clear mechanical contrast essential for origami-inspired deployment designs. Thus, the effective operating range for the dual-matrix laminate is approximately -20 °C to 100 °C, beyond which folding performance or rigidity may be compromised depending on the material region.

Figure 8: Izod impact strength of composite laminates with different fiber-matrix combinations.

Figure 8 presents the Izod impact strength of composite laminates with different fiber and matrix combinations. The conventional carbon fiber–DGEBA epoxy configuration exhibited the lowest impact resistance at 43.2 kJ/m², consistent with the known brittle nature of stiff epoxy systems. In contrast, the *p*-aramid–compliant epoxy system achieved the highest impact resistance at 89.2 kJ/m², more than doubling that of the carbon fiber–DGEBA epoxy. This significant enhancement is attributed to the high elongation and energy-absorbing nature of both the compliant epoxy and *p*-aramid fibers.

Interestingly, the carbon–compliant configuration also demonstrated markedly improved impact performance (66.8 kJ/m²), comparable to or exceeding that of the *p*-Aramid–Stiff system (67.8 kJ/m²), which is widely used in protective composite applications. These results suggest that the compliant matrix plays a dominant role in enhancing impact toughness, even when paired with inherently brittle fibers, such as carbon.

The combination of compliant matrix and high-ductility fibers not only enhances the material's ability to withstand direct impact but also holds promise for use in deployable origami structures. In such structures, deformation-based energy dissipation can further amplify impact resistance through mechanical motion, such as controlled folding, buckling, or twisting. Therefore, the *p*-Aramid–Compliant laminate emerges as a highly promising candidate for applications requiring both impact tolerance and deployability, such as protective soft robotics, aerospace shielding, or wearable armor systems.

3.4 Performance validation of the Kresling origami tube and other structure

Figure 9: (a) Cyclic load–strain response of a Kresling tube under 30–80% axial strain. (b) DMA single-cantilever test results of the compliant section over 1,000 cycles at 1,000% strain. (c) Sequential compression and expansion images of the fabricated Kresling tube. (d) Tachi–Miura polyhedron structure fabricated via dual-resin dosing process.

Figure 9 presents the cyclic performance and structural versatility of the dual-matrix composite system. Figure 9(a) shows the cyclic deployment test of a Kresling tube under axial strain ranging from 30% to 80%. After initial cycle conditioning, the load–strain curves demonstrated minimal hysteresis over 10 cycles, confirming outstanding mechanical repeatability and resilience of the integrated composite structure.

To further evaluate durability under extreme deformation, DMA single-cantilever mode tests were performed on the compliant composite section under 1,000 cycles at 1,000% strain. As shown in Figure 9(b), the storage modulus retained over 90% of its initial value, while a gradual decrease in loss modulus was observed, indicating viscoelastic stabilization and sustained energy-dissipation capability of the compliant matrix during repeated folding cycles, validating its suitability for repeated folding and actuation.

Figure 9(c) displays sequential images of the fabricated Kresling tube undergoing manual compression and expansion, visually demonstrating its reversible deformation and structural robustness. In addition, Figure 9(d) showcases a Tachi–Miura polyhedron structure manufactured using the same dual-resin dosing process, highlighting the fabrication speed and geometric versatility of the method. The ability to produce complex foldable geometries such as Tachi–Miura patterns extends the applicability of this technique to broader categories of deployable and morphing structures in soft robotics and aerospace systems.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This work introduces a dual-resin composite approach that integrates stiff and compliant epoxy matrices to engineer spatially tunable mechanical properties within a single laminate architecture. Through detailed thermal and rheological characterization, we optimized a processing window that

supports simultaneous impregnation and curing of both matrix systems. The successful application of a programmable resin-dosing process allowed for precise deposition of low-viscosity, selectively cured epoxies into designed fiber regions without interfacial delamination or phase separation. Mechanical testing demonstrated that the stiff regions provide structural rigidity suitable for maintaining defined creases during deployment, while compliant regions support reversible folding and recoverable deformation. Notably, the compliant epoxy significantly enhanced impact toughness, even when combined with brittle carbon fibers, highlighting the dominant role of matrix properties in energy absorption. Temperature-dependent DMA and long-cycle durability tests confirmed excellent thermo-mechanical stability of both regions under realistic operating conditions. Furthermore, this architecture enabled the fabrication of advanced deployable structures such as Kresling tubes and Tachi–Miura polyhedra, which exhibited robust actuation over repeated deformation. The combined advantages of low processing complexity, mechanical programmability, and long-term durability position this dual-resin strategy as a promising platform for next-generation soft robotics, deployable aerospace components, and impact-resilient morphing systems.

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